

Effects of Vegetation Loss on Cross River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla diehli*) in Cross River National Park, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research looked at the effects of habitat loss on Cross River gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla diehli*) in Cross River National Park, Cross River State, Nigeria. The study quantified vegetation loss in the study location over a period of thirty five (35) years, and also Assess tree species abundance and distribution in the study areas. The research make known the concept of habitat loss, major kinds of habitat loss, main causes of habitat loss, and effects of habitat loss and fragmentation on biodiversity conservation, effects of habitat loss and fragmentation on primates, effects of deforestation, given a detailed description of the study areas, vegetation of the park, drainage pattern of the park, stating the method of data collection. To quantify the vegetation loss in the study areas, normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) was used. Three (3) multi-date Landsat satellite imageries, Thematic Mapper (TM+) of 1991, Enhanced Thematic Mapper (ETM+) 2000 and Operational Land Imager (OLI) of 2021 were employed. The data was Analyzed using descriptive statistical tools such as bar charts, pie charts and pictograms, base on the categories of the DBH (diameter at breast height) obtained, and landsat imagery of the areas was obtained from 1990-2025. The comparative findings on tree species diversity, distribution, abundance, and important value index in the study areas showed significant differences in various ecological metrics between the two ranges (Okwango and Anape). The Okwango range had 1,078 individual trees, marginally more than the Anape range, which had 1,065 individuals in its sample. The study concludes that forest and vegetation cover showed a steady decline throughout the period. The net reduction of nearly 37,500 hectares indicates the adverse impact of anthropogenic activities such as deforestation, agricultural expansion, and urban sprawl. And recommended that, land surveys should be carried out to determine the rate of encroachment into the Park by loggers and farmers, and efforts should be made to adequately protect the study area, since it is one of the few location in the country where some valuable tropical and indigenous trees species can be found.

Keywords: *Gorilla gorilla diehli, anthropogenic activities, vegetation loss, biodiversity conservation.*

Suggested citation: Adendem M.N., Uloko I.J., Tyouwa A.T.B., Iwar M.I., & Williams, M.M. (2025). Effects of Vegetation Loss on Cross River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla diebli*) in Cross River National Park, Cross River State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 2(6), 136-162. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2025.2(6).13

Introduction

Habitat loss refers to the reduction in the amount of space where a particular species, or group of species can survive and reproduce. Habitat loss is a consequence of human activities such as agriculture, urbanization, deforestation, resource extraction, alteration of the sea-floor due to trawling (fishing), or the release of pollutants. Habitat loss can also occur due to environmental changes, such as volcanic eruptions or tsunamis, or changes in climate or sea level, which today are largely the result of human activities. Habitat loss can decrease biodiversity and alters species ranges and interactions (Kelhoukhrienuo Metha, et al., 2023).

Habitat loss due to destruction, fragmentation, or degradation of habitat is the primary threat to the survival of wildlife in the United States. When an ecosystem has been dramatically changed by human activities such as agriculture, oil and gas exploration, commercial development, or water diversion it may no longer be able to provide the food, water, cover, and places to raise the young ones that wildlife needs to survive. Every day there are fewer places left that wildlife can call home (Kellerman, n.d.).

Objectives of the Study

The work has two specific aims which are to:

1. Quantify Vegetation loss in the study location
2. Assess tree species abundance and distribution in the study areas.

Statement of Problem

Tropical biodiversity is in serious trouble basically due to human actions. These threats can be group into two; direct or proximate threats and indirect or underlying threats (CBD, 2010). National Parks are being destroyed and wildlife species being lost at alarming rate. There is urgent need for continuous assessment of its present status. However, Gorillas are among the world's most threatened species of primates (Rylands *et al.* 2008a; Schipper *et al.* 2008; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). However, currently there is few information into the effect of habitat loss on the population of these species and whether these effects vary across primate species (Arroyo-Rodriguez *et al.* 2013b; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Nonetheless, most studies on Gorillas focus on the effects of patch-scale fragmentation on gorillas and have ignored the influence of habitat loss at broader scales (Arroyo-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2013a) and (Carretero-Pinzón *et al.* 2015) and Carretero-Pinzón, (2016). This is a critical limitation because species' responses to habitat loss and fragmentation are influenced by the scale at which these processes occur (Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

Justification of the Study

An increased human population and the animal trade market still being strong are causing overexploitation, habitat loss and species extinction, (Arroyo-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2013b; Oskarsson, 2014). This research will therefore be an additional study towards providing current data on tree species in the study areas for effective conservation and management. This will guide conservators and managers of National Parks to make informed decisions that will guide against such loss of species. This research will be of benefit to conservation organizations, students, research institutions among others.

Scope of the Study

The study is limited to Cross-River National Park in Cross River State, Nigeria. The study assessed the Effects of Vegetation Loss on Cross River Gorilla (*Gorilla gorilla Diehli*) In Cross River National Park, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

The Concept of Habitat Loss

Habitat loss refers to the reduction in the amount of space where a particular species, or group of species can survive and reproduce. Habitat loss is a consequence of human activities such as agriculture, urbanization, deforestation, resource extraction, alteration of the sea-floor due to trawling (fishing), or the release of pollutants. Habitat loss can also occur due to environmental changes, such as volcanic eruptions or tsunamis, or changes in climate or sea level, which today are largely the result of human activities. Habitat loss can decrease biodiversity and alters species ranges and interactions (National Wildlife Federation, n.d.).

Habitat loss due to destruction, fragmentation, or degradation of habitat is the primary threat to the survival of wildlife in the United States. When an ecosystem has been dramatically changed by human activities such as agriculture, oil and gas exploration, commercial development, or water diversion it may no longer be able to provide the food, water, cover, and places to raise the young ones that wildlife needs to survive. Every day there are fewer places left that wildlife can call home (National Wildlife Federation, n.d.).

Major Kinds of Habitat Loss

Habitat destruction: A bulldozer pushing down trees is the iconic image of habitat destruction. Other ways people directly destroy habitat include filling in wetlands, dredging rivers, mowing fields, and cutting down trees. **Habitat fragmentation:** Much of the remaining terrestrial wildlife habitat in Nigeria has been cut up into fragments by roads and development. Aquatic species' habitats have been fragmented by dams and water diversions (National Wildlife Federation, n.d.). These fragments of habitat may not be large or connected enough to support species that need a large territory where they can find mates and food. The loss and fragmentation of habitats makes it difficult for migratory species to find places to rest and feed along their migration routes. **Habitat degradation:** Pollution, invasive species, and disruption of ecosystem processes (such as changing the intensity of fires in an ecosystem) are some of the way's habitats can become so degraded, they no longer support native wildlife (National Wildlife Federation, n.d.).

Main Causes of Habitat Loss

Agriculture: Much of the habitat loss from agriculture was done long ago when settlers converted forests and prairies to cropland. Today, there is increasing pressure to redevelop conservation lands for high-priced food and biofuel crops (National Wildlife Federation, n.d.). **Land conversion for development:** The conversion of lands that once provided wildlife habitat to housing developments, roads, office parks, strip malls, parking lots and industrial sites continues, even during the current economic crisis (National Wildlife Federation, n.d.). **Water development:** Dams and other water diversions siphon off and disconnect waters, changing hydrology and water chemistry (when nutrients are not able to flow downstream). During the dry season, the Colorado River has little to no water in it by the time it reaches the Sea of Cortez (National Wildlife Federation, n.d.). **Pollution:** Freshwater wildlife are most impacted by pollution. Pollutants such as untreated sewage, mining waste, acid rain, fertilizers and pesticides concentrate in rivers, lakes and wetlands and eventually end up in estuaries and the food web (National Wildlife Federation, n.d.). **Climate change:** The emerging driver of habitat loss is climate change.

Wildlife that need the cool temperatures of high elevations, may soon run out of habitat. Coastal wildlife may find their habitat underwater as sea levels rise (Kellerman, n.d.).

Effects of Habitat Loss and Fragmentation on Biodiversity Conservation

It is generally accepted that the effects of habitat loss on biodiversity are strongly negative and outweigh the effects of fragmentation (Menz *et al.* 2013; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). However, habitat fragmentation also has strong and generally degrading effects on biodiversity and ecological processes (Haddad *et al.* 2015). In addition, matrix composition (Villard & Metzger, 2014; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016) and edge effects (Laurence, 2010, Laurence *et al.* 2007; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016) are also important for species persistence in fragmented landscapes. Understanding the effects of habitat loss, fragmentation and composition of the matrix on species is important for conservation biology (Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

Habitat loss and fragmentation impact not only the presence and abundance of species but also their behaviour (Morante-Filho *et al.* 2015; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Changes in dispersal patterns, feeding behaviours, predation risk and population dynamics have been observed as a consequence of habitat loss and fragmentation in different groups of vertebrates (Boyle & Smith 2010a; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). For example, changes in group size and behavioural patterns (feeding and/or traveling times) have been observed in primate species living in fragments due to reduction in fragment size (Boyle & Smith 2010a; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). In birds and mammals, predation risk seems to increase with fragmentation and depends on various factors such as distance to the edge, the type of habitat and predator ecology (Poulin & Villard 2011; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). The observed changes due to habitat loss and fragmentation vary depending on their drivers and the scale at which these processes occur (Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

The drivers of habitat loss and fragmentation depend on the region in which they occur. For example, fire is important for habitat loss in areas of boreal forest, while human population growth and the expansion of productive activities such as agriculture are more important in tropical zones of South America, Africa and Asia (Hansen *et al.* 2013; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). The effects of habitat loss and fragmentation also vary with the magnitude of the drivers and the scale at which those drives occur, which can determine the species extinction thresholds (Pardini *et al.* 2010; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

Extinction threshold theory states that there is a minimum amount of habitat for a given species for it to persist in a landscape (Pardini *et al.* 2010; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). This threshold is proposed to occur when less than 30 % of the habitat remains but may vary depending on the species being studied (Adendem *et al.* 2020, Morante-Filho *et al.* 2015; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Although differentiating the effects of habitat loss and fragmentation on species extinction thresholds are difficult due to the general high correlation between fragmentation and habitat loss metrics, habitat loss has been identified as the main factor affecting extinction thresholds (Pardini *et al.* 2010; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Habitat loss is the most important factor because it drives the carrying capacity of habitats and it affect the reproduction rates of species (Pardini *et al.* 2010; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

Habitat loss and fragmentation are processes occurring at the landscape scale, but can vary with the spatial extent and resolution of the landscape (Wu & Li, 2006; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Scale is defined as “spatial or temporal dimension of an object or process, characterized by both grain and extent” (Turner *et al.* 2001; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Where grain refers to the finest spatial resolution at which an object or process is observed and the extent refers to the size of the overall study area (Turner *et al.* 2001; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). In fragmented landscapes, the spatial configuration and composition of the landscape vary with the scale at which these processes are observed and with the scale at which species perceive it (Fahrig *et al.* 2011; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Scale is referred to as the space and time dimension of the process of study (Wu & Li 2006). In the absence of a priori knowledge of the scale that is important to the species of study, multi-scale analyses have been used to determine the spatial scale at which management actions need to be taken depending on the species of concern (Martin & Fahrig, 2012; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

Studies using a landscape approach allows us to understand how habitat loss and fragmentation influence species population dynamics in terms of the composition and spatial configuration of landscapes and how these elements affect species and ecosystem function (Fahrig *et al.* 2011; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). A strong focus on the scales that are appropriate for the organisms being studied is important to understand the interactions between populations and spatial patterns (Wu & Li, 2006; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016) and how these interactions affect species responses. This is particularly true in tropical forests, where the rate of deforestation is one of the main causes of threats for species dependant such as the Cross River Gorilla (Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

Effects of Habitat Loss and Fragmentation on Primates

More than 50% of primate species are threatened globally (Schwitzer *et al.* 2015; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Habitat loss and fragmentation are two of the main drivers of primate species declines (Schwitzer *et al.* 2015; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Although these processes occur at the landscape level, most primate research has been focussed on effects of site and patch scales, with little focus on the landscape scale effects (Arroyo-Rodriguez *et al.* 2013a, Arroyo-Rodriguez & Fahrig, 2014, Carretero-Pinzón *et al.* 2016). Therefore, the understanding of the effect of site, patch and landscape variables on primate species' responses to habitat loss and fragmentation is still unclear, but necessary for primate conservation (Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

Primate studies have followed three different approaches to understand fragmentation and/or habitat loss effects on species responses. Studies based on the theory of island biogeography that see primates from a patch perspective, isolated in a hostile matrix, with an emphasis at the site or patch scale (Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Meta-population theory-based studies that include primate movement between fragments in terms of dispersal without an emphasis on the use of the matrix and non-habitat landscape elements, and landscape ecology-based studies which include the landscape scale to understand primate patterns of patch occupation and abundance, including matrix uses (Arroyo-Rodriguez *et al.* 2013b; Boyle & Smith, 2010b; Pyritz *et al.* 2010; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Most studies have been conducted using the first approach to assess group changes in ecological and behavioural variables comparing one or several groups in small fragments to one or two groups of primates in a larger fragment or continuous forest (Arroyo-Rodriguez & Dias 2010; Abondano & Link, 2012; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Although we have information on primate species responses to changes in patch size (Carretero-Pinzón *et al.* 2016), the effect of habitat loss and fragmentation processes at different scale has been done only in a few studies (Thornton *et al.* 2011; Arroyo-Rodriguez *et al.* 2013b; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

The species-area relationship has been studied globally and for some specific regions for primates, concluding that primate species richness increases with forest patch size, in general (Benchimol & Peres, 2013; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). This finding supports one of the predictions of island biogeography theory that states that bigger fragments have more species compared to smaller fragments (Boyle & Smith 2010b; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

However, primate studies in fragments have also highlighted the importance of small fragments and the matrix surrounding those fragments for the persistence of primate species in fragmented areas (Boyle & Smith, 2010b; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Most threatened primate species only persist in highly fragmented areas, therefore, understanding the effects of habitat variables at different scales (site, patch and landscape scales) will help us to implement better informed conservation actions for these species (Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

Primate responses to the effects of habitat loss and fragmentation are also highly variable across continents and species (Arroyo-Rodriguez and Dias, 2010; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Changes in behaviour, densities, abundance and presence have been observed that seem to be the product of habitat loss and fragmentation (Arroyo-Rodriguez and Dias, 2010; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

Primate persistence in forest fragments not only depends on fragment size effects but also can be affected by the time that the fragment was formed and other pressures associated with the fragmentation process, such as hunting and edge effects (Boyle & Smith, 2010b; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). There is evidence that some species of old-world monkeys (Africa and Asia) have greater resilience to changes produced by human activities, (Benchimol & Peres, 2013; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

However, threats faced by primates in fragmented landscapes can also be considered at short scales of time, such as seasonal variability's in resources abundance that could be due to the product of slight variations in local climate (Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Slight variations in climate patterns such as rainfall seems to also affect primate species' responses to habitat loss and fragmentation in fragmented landscapes because of their effects on seasonal fruit production, (Arroyo-Rodriguez and Dias, 2010; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

Primate species face additional pressures due to their close proximity to human settlements and to production activities site such as agriculture. These pressures can exacerbate (make worse) the effects of habitat loss and fragmentation on primate species, depending on species' life history traits. For example, the large space requirement of some large bodied primate species living in large groups at times has been overcome by utilising crops and urban resources as part of their diet (Campbell-Smith *et al.*, 2012; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

In addition, some traits such as large body size and diet specialization seem to make species with these traits more sensitive to other concomitant and anthropogenic pressures such as: selective logging and hunting, (Chapman *et al.*, 2012; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). The interaction of these factors has been poorly studied (Dunn *et al.* 2014). Conservation strategies on primates have focused on the selection of areas to conserve specific primate species or communities, focussing on population and threat analysis, (Carlsen *et al.*, 2012, Dunn *et al.*, 2014; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). However, the rapid deforestation of tropical areas has led to changes in strategies for area selection for primate conservation in recent years. Primates are among the world's most threatened mammals, (Dunn *et al.* 2014; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). And they commonly occur in landscapes subjected to high levels of habitat modification (Marsh *et al.*, 2013; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

However, currently there is lack of general insights into the effect of habitat loss and fragmentation for primates and whether their effects vary across primate species, (Boyle and Smith, 2010; Arroyo-Rodriguez and Fahrig, 2014; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Understanding whether any generalities can be made about responses of primates to habitat loss and fragmentation is important because species vary remarkably in their life history, characteristics and the types of habitats that they occupy, (Defler 2010; Mittermeier *et al.*, 2013; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

Effects of Deforestation

Deforestation continues at an alarming rate in the tropics, (Hansen *et al.* 2013; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). Understanding the spatial distributions of wildlife populations is important for their conservation and management, especially in tropical areas (Guisan *et al.* 2013; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

Species' distributions are influenced not only by the characteristics of individual patches but also by the structure and composition of the surrounding landscape (Guisan *et al.* 2013; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016). An important consideration is the amount of suitable habitat which relates to habitat loss, (Arroyo Rodriguez *et al.* 2013; Carretero-Pinzón, 2016).

According to the United Nations' Human Development Program (UNDP) the lack of steady economic growth in many tropical regions harbouring primate populations and habitats makes it difficult or impossible to significantly reduce rural poverty, which in turn will continue to foster enormous pressure on natural habitats and weakly protected reserves (UNDP, 2009; Oskarsson, 2014). As a result, conservation approaches are required not only within, but also outside of protected area boundaries. The

matrix (environment) of surrounding agriculture habitat may play an important role in long-term primate and biodiversity preservation and must be considered in landscape-level approaches to conservation. (Daily *et al.* 2003; Oskarsson, 2014). They also provide food and cash income for millions of rural households and comprise the basis of regional and national economies in many countries, (Fox *et al.*, 2000; Estrada, 2009).

In African folklore, animals often appear as central or supporting characters, such as heroes or tricksters (Peek and Yankah, 2004; Cronin, Riaco, & Hearn, 2013). Depending on an animal's role or character, it may be culturally tolerated or protected by a society through informal institutions such as social taboos. Taboos that prevent human harassment or killing of wild species may prove critical in their conservation (Jones *et al.* 2008; Cronin, Riaco, & Hearn, 2013). Pressures for land use have been a major cause of tropical rain forest loss and fragmentation throughout the world (Donald, 2004; Oskarsson, 2014), and a major cause of increases in rates of species extinction in recent decades (Laurance *et al.* 2007; Oskarsson, 2014). Fragmentation of habitat and stochastic (random) forces, along with the increasing rarity of suitable habitat, play an important role in further declines of animal populations and species at the local level (Helne *et al.*, 2004; Oskarsson, 2014).

Materials and Methods

The Study Area

Cross River National Park (CRNP) is situated between latitudes 05°05'N and 06°29'N and longitudes 08°15'E and 09°30'E in Cross River State, south-eastern Nigeria. The Park has two separate sections, Okwangwo division established in 1991 and Oban division established in 1988, (Ezebilo, 2013). The park has a total area of about 4,000km², most of which consists of primary moist tropical rainforests in the North and Central parts, with mangrove swamps on the coastal zones. Parts of the park belong to the Guinea-Congolian region, with a closed canopy and scattered emergent trees reaching 40-50 meters in height, (Nigeria National Park Service, 2015).

Figure 1. Map of Nigeria Showing Cross River State, showing the study Locations
Source: Field Survey, (2025)

The Park was established by the Federal Ministry Government Decree in 1991, with the Cross-River gorilla chosen as the theme animal, (Laura, 2013). The park is considered a part of the Guineo-Congolian biodiversity hotspot (Ezebilo, 2013; Olory, 2018). It covers an area of approximately 4,000 km² that harbours mainly humid tropical rainforest and swamps (Olory, 2018; Nneji, et al., 2021).

The biological uniqueness of south-eastern Nigeria is exceptional for Cross River National Park (CRNP), which houses one of the oldest tropical rainforests in Africa, and the last remaining rainforest in Nigeria (Olory, 2018; Nneji, et al., 2021). Previous studies estimated the vegetation to have evolved over 60 million years ago, with more than 2500 plant, 600 bird, 70 snake, and 100 mammal species (Ezebilo, 2013; Olory, 2018; Nneji, et al., 2021). Approximately 90% of all Nigerian butterflies and roughly 30% of butterfly species in sub-Saharan Africa occur in Park, (Olory, 2018; Nneji, et al., 2021).

The park was first proposed in 1965, but serious planning did not start until 1988. The World Wide Fund for Nature - UK played a leading role for the plan to establish the park in two divisions separated by farmland and the Cross-River valley, with a budget of \$49.9 million. The plan envisaged villagers in the buffer zone being involved in running the park and being given development aid, (John, 2002; Nneji, et al., 2021).

The original plan was not fully implemented, and the park established in 1991 only included existing forest reserves. After a small amount of initial aid, the funding dried up and the villagers became hostile to the park administration, (John, 2002; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.). An amending decree in 1999 converted the Nigerian National Park Service, which runs the park, into a paramilitary outfit with increased powers, (Laura, 2003; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.).

The Oban Hills Division is 2,800 km² in area, centred on coordinates 5°25'0"N 8°35'0"E, (BirdLife International, 2010). The division shares a long border with Korup National Park in the Republic of Cameroon, forming a single protected ecological zone, (Nigeria National Park Service, 2013). The division has a rugged terrain, rising from 100m in the river valleys to over 1,000m in the mountains. The soils are highly vulnerable to leaching and erosion where stripped of plant cover. The rainy season lasts from March to November, with annual rainfall of over 3,500mm. The northern part is drained by the Cross river and its tributaries. The southern parts are drained by the Calabar, Kwa and Korup rivers, (BirdLife International, 2010; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.).

The division is mostly covered with lowland rainforest. Typical tree species include *Musanga cecropioides* the African corkwood tree or umbrella tree, *Irvingia gabonensis* bush mango *Berlinia confusa*, *Coula edulis*, *Hannoa klaineana*, *Klainedoxa gabonensis* African mahogany and red ironwood, (BirdLife International, 2010; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.). About 1,568 plant species have been identified, of which 77 are endemic to Nigeria, (Nigeria National Park Service, 2012; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.). These include 1,303 flowering plants, 141 lichens and 56 moss species, (BirdLife International, 2010; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.). Torben Larsen collected almost 600 species of butterfly in the Oban division in 1995, and estimated that there may be 950 species in total in the division, (John, 2002; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.).

Okwangwo division is centred on coordinates 6°17'00"N 9°14'00"E. It is made up of the former Boshi, Okwangwo and Boshi Extension Forest Reserves, (Uwem, 1997; Fitz, Adenle, & Speranza, 2022). The division has an area of about 920 km² at an altitude of 150 - 1,700m above sea level. It is separated from the Oban division to the south by about 50km of disturbed rainforest. It lies south-west of the Obudu Plateau and immediately to the east of the Afi River Forest Reserve, separated from this reserve by the Mbe Mountains Community Forest, (BirdLife International, 2010; Fitz, Adenle, & Speranza, 2022).

The Takamanda Forest Reserve in the Republic of Cameroon shares a border with the Okwangwo division to the east, (BirdLife International, 2010; Fitz, Adenle, & Speranza, 2022). In November 2008 Takamanda was upgraded to a National Park through a joint project with the Wildlife Conservation Society and the government of Cameroon, with protection of the endangered Cross River gorilla a major

objective. The 676km² Takamanda National Park will also help conserve forest elephants, chimpanzees, and drills (Fitz, Adenle, & Speranza, 2022).

The ground is rugged, with rocky ridges and outcrops. The highest points are in the Sankwala Mountains in the north (1,700 m) and in the Mbe Mountains in the south-west (1,000m). Annual rainfall may be as much as 4,280 mm, mostly falling in the wet season between March and November (Fitz, Adenle, & Speranza, 2022). The division is drained by the Oyi, Bemil and Okon rivers, tributaries of the Cross River. The high ridge-tops are covered in montane grasslands, with relict forests in the valleys. Lower down, the division is covered by lowland rainforests, with areas of savanna where humans have destroyed the forests. The soils in the highland and lowland areas are vulnerable to erosion and leaching when stripped of their plant cover, (BirdLife International, 2010; Fitz, Adenle, & Speranza, 2022).

The park has four departments: Park Protection and Conservation, Ecotourism, Park Engineering and Maintenance, and Finance and Administration (Wikipedia contributor, n.d.). In 2010, 250 of the total 320 personnel worked in Park Protection and Conservation, mostly male due to the rigors of the job, based at twelve ranger stations. This number is inadequate given the size of the territory to be patrolled. Despite attempts at training, many of the rangers are poorly qualified and are dissatisfied with pay, equipment, motivation and career prospects (Wikipedia contributor, n.d.).

Vegetation of the Park

The park consists of primary moist tropical rainforests in the North and Central parts, with mangrove swamps on the coastal zones. Parts of the park belong to the Guinea-Congolian region, with a closed canopy and scattered emergent trees reaching 40 or 50 meters in height, (Cross River National Park, 2014; Wildlife Conservation Society Nigeria, n.d.). The park has one of the oldest rainforests in Africa, and has been identified as a biodiversity hot spot, (Cross River National Park, 2014). The Park has two divisions Oban and Okwango (Wildlife Conservation Society Nigeria, n.d.).

The Oban division is known to harbour 1,568 species of plants of which 77 species are endemic to Nigeria, three new records for Nigeria and one probably new to science. (Conor and Martin, 1989; Olory, 2018). Several other vulnerable plants including timber species, NTFPs (Non timber forest products), medicinal plants, among others also abound in the Park. Of interest are medicinal plant species, *Anceistocladus korupensis*, which is suspected to have potent ingredient for the cure of the dreaded HIV/AIDS (Olory, 2018). And *Prunus africana* known to have potency for cure of prostate cancer. The division is mostly covered with lowland rainforest. Typical tree species include *Musanga cecropioides*, the African corkwood tree or umbrella tree, *Irvingia gabonensis* bush mango *Berlinia confusa*, *Coula edulis*, *Hannoa klaineana*, *Klainedoxa gabonensis*, African mahogany and red ironwood. (Wikipedia contributor, n.d.)

While as in the Okwango division Obot *et al.*, (1996) recorded a total of 1,545 plant specimens representing 98 families in Okwangwo Division alone. Of these, six (6) were said to be new records to Nigeria and four probably new to science (Olory, 2018). The new records to Nigeria are: *Asplenium cornutum* (Aspleniaceae), *Arthropteris monocarpa* (Davalliaceae); *Bulbophyllum bequaertii* (Orchidaceae); *Bulbophyllum odicum* (Orchidaceae); *Disperis nitida* (Orchidaceae) and *Habenaria obovata* (Orchidaceae), while the possible species new to science include: *Trydactyle* spp (Orchidaceae); *Uapaca* spp (Euphorbiaceae); *Habenaria* spp. (Orchidaceae) and *Afrocalathea flavida* spp. (Maranthaceae), (Obot *et al.*, 1996; Olory, 2018).

Drainage Pattern of the Park

The Park is divided into two, Oban division and Okwango division. The Oban division has a rugged terrain, rising from 100m in the river valleys to over 1,000 m in the mountains. The soils are highly vulnerable to leaching and erosion where stripped of plant cover. The rainy season lasts from March to November, with annual rainfall of over 3,500mm. The northern part is drained by the Cross river and its

tributaries. The southern parts are drained by the Calabar, Kwa and Korup rivers, (Cross River National Park, 2014; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.).

While as in the Okwango division the ground is rugged, with rocky ridges and outcrops. The highest points are in the Sankwala Mountains in the north (1,700 m) and in the Mbe Mountains in the south-west (1,000m). Annual rainfall may be as much as 4,280mm, mostly falling in the wet season between March and November. The division is drained by the Oyi, Bembi and Okon rivers, tributaries of the Cross River. The high ridge-tops are covered in montane grasslands, with relict forests in the valleys. Lower down, the division is covered by lowland rainforests, with areas of savanna where humans have destroyed the forests. The soils in the highland and lowland areas are vulnerable to erosion and leaching when stripped of their plant cover, (Cross River National Park, 2014; Wikipedia contributor, n.d.).

Method of Data Collection

To quantify the vegetation loss in the study locations. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was used. This method was used by (Yager et al., 2022) in Afi Mountain Wildlife Sanctuary, Cross River State, Nigeria. Three (3) multi-date Landsat satellite imageries, Thematic Mapper (TM+) of 1991, Enhanced Thematic Mapper (ETM+) 2000 and Operational Land Imager (OLI) of 2021 were employed (Yager, et al., 2022). A supervised classification method was carried out based on level 1 classification scheme of Yager et al., (2022). This was used to classify the identify vegetation cover categories into four: 1990-2000, 2001-2010, 2011-2020, and 2021-2025. Four land use and land cover features were used for the study (Yager, et al., 2022). That is; Forest area, Agricultural land, grass land, and built up areas.

Quadrats (plots) were also laid in the sample areas (Okwango Range and Anape Range). This involved the total enumeration of all tree plants above 1m height and diameter of not less than 11cm, from 25×25m² quadrants (plots) within a distance of one kilometres (1km), a total of five possible quadrants or plots of 25×25m² were laid in each of the twenty sampled transects giving a total of one hundred (100) plots dimension of 25×25m². For each transect, vegetation surveys was conducted in five (5) 25×25m² plots, located every 200m along each transect. For each plot, all trees with diameter at breast height (DBH) of >10 cm were recorded.

Data Analysis

descriptive statistical tools such as bar charts, pie charts and pictograms were used to analyse the data base on the categories of the DBH (diameter at breast height) and landsat imagery of the areas was obtained from 1990-2025 as seen in the result.

Results

Table 1 indicated a comparative result of tree species diversity, distribution, and abundance in the study areas. The result shows significant differences in various ecological metrics between the two ranges (Okwango and Anape). The Okwango range had 1,078 individual trees, marginally more than the Anape range, which had 1,065 individuals in its sample. The statistical significance of this difference is indicated by the p-value of 0.00 ($p < 1$). There are more taxa in Okwango Range compare to Anape Range. Okwango had seventy eight tree species richness while as Anape had thirty six (36), and the p-value of 0.00 ($p < 1$) indicates that this difference is statistically significant.

The Dominance_D index, which measures the probability that two individuals randomly selected from a sample belong to the same species, shows values of 0.05 for Anape and 0.04 for Okwango. The p-value of 0.10 indicates that this difference is not statistically significant, indicating similar levels of species dominance in the two ranges. The Simpson1-D index, reflecting the probability that two individuals randomly selected from a sample belong to different species, presents values of 0.95 for Anape and 0.96 for Okwango, with a p-value of 0.288, indicating no significant difference between the two areas.

The Shannon H index, which accounts for both abundance and evenness of species, is higher in the Okwango range (3.70) than the Anape range (3.22), with a p-value of 0.01, indicating a statistically significant difference. This showed higher species diversity in Okwango. Conversely, the Evenness (e^H/S) index, measuring how evenly individuals are distributed among the species present, is higher in Anape (0.69) than in Okwango (0.52), with a p-value of 0.00, signifying a significant difference and indicating a more even distribution of individuals among species in Anape.

The Brillouin index, another measure of diversity that accounts for the number of species and their relative abundances, is higher in Okwango (3.57) compared to Anape (3.14), with a p-value of 0.00, indicating a significant difference. The Menhinick index, which relates species richness to the total number of individuals, is also higher in Okwango (2.38) than in Anape (1.10), with a p-value of 0.00, further highlighting the greater species richness in Okwango.

The Margalef index, another species richness measure, shows a higher value for Okwango (11.03) compared to Anape (5.02), with a p-value of 0.00, indicating a significant difference. The Equitability_J index, which measures species evenness, presents similar values for both ranges (0.90 for Anape and 0.85 for Okwango), with a p-value of 0.06, suggesting no significant difference.

The Fisher_alpha index, reflecting the diversity within a community, is higher in Okwango (19.31) than the Anape range (7.19), with a p-value of 0.00, indicating a significant difference. The Berger-Parker index, which measures the dominance of the most abundant species, shows values of 0.10 for Anape and 0.09 for Okwango, with a p-value of 0.26, suggesting no significant difference in species dominance between the two ranges. The Chao-1 index, an estimator of total species richness accounting for unseen species, is higher in Okwango (85.80) compared to Anape (36.33), with a p-value of 0.00, indicating a significant difference and suggesting that Okwango may harbour more undiscovered species.

Table 1. Tree Species Diversity, Distribution and Abundance Indices in the Study Areas

Indices	Anape range	Okwnago range	p-value	Remak
Individuals	1065 ^b	1078 ^a	0.00	**
Taxa_S	36 ^b	78 ^a	0.00	**
Dominance_D	0.05 ^a	0.04 ^a	0.10	NS
Simpson_1-D	0.95 ^a	0.96 ^a	0.28	NS
Shannon_H	3.22 ^b	3.70 ^a	0.01	*
Evenness_e ^H /S	0.69 ^a	0.52 ^b	0.00	**
Brillouin	3.14 ^b	3.57 ^a	0.00	**
Menhinick	1.10 ^b	2.38 ^a	0.00	**
Margalef	5.02 ^b	11.03 ^a	0.00	**
Equitability_J	0.90 ^a	0.85 ^a	0.06	NS
Fisher_alpha	7.19 ^b	19.31 ^a	0.00	**
Berger-Parker	0.10 ^a	0.09 ^a	0.26	NS
Chao-1	36.33 ^b	85.80 ^a	0.00	**

Note: Rows with different superscripts (alphabets) are statistically significant at 0.05 levels. *(significant) NS (Not Significant) ** (Highly Significant)

Source: Field Survey, (2025)

The result of species composition in Anape and Okwango range as shown on (Table 2 - Appendix) shows differences in tree distribution, frequency and basal area. These differences are expressed using key ecological indicators such as Relative Density (RD), Relative Dominance (RDo), and the Importance Value Index (IVI), which show each species' presence and functional role within the forest ecosystem. The result on Table 2 showed that, some tree species are confined to only one of the two forest ranges.

For instance, species such as *Alafia barteri*, *Albizia zygia*, and *Allablackia floribunda* were found solely in the Okwango Range. In contrast, *Anogeisus leiocarpa*, *Christiana africana*, and *Hannoa undulata* were exclusive to the Anape Range. The Okwango Range recorded a higher diversity of tree species overall. It included a wider range of high- and low-frequency species, showing a more complex and dynamic forest structure. This richness points to high ecological variability and possibly more diverse microhabitats within the Okwango Range.

The Importance Value Index (IVI) is used to determine the ecological dominance of a species by integrating its relative density and dominance. A high IVI indicates that a species is not only numerous but also occupies a significant proportion of the forest's total basal area. In the Anape Range, *Christiana africana* recorded the highest IVI (6.37), indicating its important role in shaping the forest structure. Other species with high IVIs includes *Harungana madagascariensis* (4.67), *Antiaris toxicaria* (4.85), and *Entandopbragma angolense* (4.14), all of which appear to be significant in the range. In contrast, the Okwango Range showed different patterns of dominance. For example, *Bambax buonopozense* had a very high IVI (8.90), despite being represented by only one individual, due to its exceptionally large basal area. Similarly, *Allablackia floribunda* had IVI of 5.10 and *Cylicodiscus gabunensis* had IVI of 4.20 also having a strong ecological influence in this forest, even when their frequencies were relatively low.

Several species in both ranges had lower IVIs, showing their rarity or minimal contribution to the total basal area. In the Anape Range, species like *Holarrhena floribunda* had IVI of 0.36 and *Gossweilerodendron balsamiferum* had IVI of 2.21 which had limited ecological presence. Similarly, in the Okwango Range, species such as *Barteria nigritana*, *Chrysophyllum albidum*, and *Cola caricifolia* showed very low IVI values. These species may exist in marginal habitats or be experiencing population declines, potentially due to natural competition or anthropogenic pressures. Some species were found in both Anape and Okwango but varied in their ecological prominence (relative importance). For example, *Baphia nitida* occurred more frequently and had a slightly higher IVI in Okwango (3.91) compared to Anape (3.69), indicating higher ecological influence. *Dalbergia latifolia* had similar IVI values in both locations (1.58 in Anape Range and 1.67 in Okwango), indicating a relatively uniform presence across both locations. *Distemonanthus benthamianus* had a significantly higher IVI in Okwango (2.82) than in Anape (1.34), revealing area differences in its ecological role or site preference.

Table 3 explained the distribution of families with high (>5.0) Importance Values index (FIVI) in Anape and Okwango range revealing distinct patterns, with the Fabaceae family being the most dominant in both ecosystems. In the Anape range, the Fabaceae family has an FIVI of 20.84, indicating its substantial contribution to the ecosystem's structure and function. Apocynaceae and Meliaceae families also have high importance family value with FIVI values index of 15.79 and 10.34, respectively. In the Okwango range, the Malvaceae and Sapotaceae families have a higher presence, with FIVI values of 17.50 and 11.83, respectively. The Fabaceae family remains dominant in this ranges, with an FIVI of 27.44. The Olacaceae and Rubiaceae families have moderate FIVI values in the Okwango range.

The Fabaceae family is the most dominant in the two ecosystems (Ranges). Certain families are present in one range but not the other. The variation in FIVI values between the two ranges was influenced maybe by environmental factors, such as climate, soil, or topography, which shape the composition and structure of plant communities. The result of FIVI values in the areas (Anape and Okwango Range) gives an understanding of the ecological significance of plant families and their distribution patterns, with implications for conservation and management efforts that aim to preserve the integrity of these ecosystems.

Table 3. Distribution of Families with High Family Importance Values (FIVI) (>5.0) in Anape and Okwango Range

Family Names	FIVI	
	Anape range	Okwango range
Apocynaceae	15.79	-
Euphorbiaceae	5.95	-
Fabaceae	20.84	27.44
Malvaceae	9.95	17.50
Meliaceae	10.34	-
Moraceae	6.48	-
Ochnaceae	5.27	-
Olacaceae	-	6.75
Rubiaceae	-	7.28
Sapotaceae	-	11.83

Source: Field Survey, (2025)

The diameter distribution of tree stands is an essential aspect of forest structure analysis, which shows the trend, stand composition, regeneration status, and the developmental stage of the forest ecosystem. In Figure 2, the tree diameters were distributed into varying classes, and their corresponding frequencies were recorded for the two forest ranges Anape and Okwango within the study area. Based on the result, the total number of trees recorded was 1,065 in Anape and 1,078 in Okwango, showing a comparable sampling effort and forest density across the two ranges. The ranges are primarily dominated by trees in the lower diameter class (10–110 cm).

Anape Range recorded 715 trees, while Okwango Range recorded an even higher count of 960 trees in this size class. This shows that a large proportion of the trees in both sites are relatively young or small in diameter, indicating active regeneration and a healthy recruitment of new growth.

Figure 2. Diameter Distribution of Tree Stands in the Study Areas

Source: Field Survey, (2025)

As diameter size increases, the frequency of trees steadily declines in both forest ranges; for instance, in the 110–210 cm class, tree counts dropped significantly to 158 in Anape Range and 90 in Okwango

Range. The trend continues, with only a few trees recorded in the larger diameter classes. In the 310–410 cm class, Anape Range recorded 40 trees, while Okwango Range had just 2 trees. The trend is consistent through the upper class diameter (>910 cm), where both ranges had only 2 trees each.

This descending pattern is typical of natural forests with continuous recruitment and uneven-aged stand structures, where many smaller (younger) trees coexist with fewer larger (older) ones. It reflects a “reverse-J shape” distribution curve, which is characteristic of sustainably regenerating forests.

The two ranges show a similar overall pattern, however, there are some differences. Okwango Range has a higher number of small-diameter trees (10–110cm), indicating either more successful natural regeneration or possibly recent disturbances (such as selective logging) that opened up space for new seedlings. Anape Range recorded more trees in the middle and upper diameter classes (110–310cm), indicating that it may host relatively older or more mature tree stands than Okwango. Above 310 cm, the number of large trees becomes minimal in the ranges, showing a rate of scarcity of old-growth individuals.

The results in Table 4 showed distinct trends in land use and land cover (LULC) over a thirty-five-years period, capturing dynamic shifts across three primary categories: farm/bare land, built-up area, and forest/vegetation area. These changes showed evolving land utilization patterns in both Ranges (Okwango and Anape). In 1990, farm and bare land occupied approximately 12,167.5 hectares, increasing to 12,769.0 hectares in 2000, 30,510.9 hectares in 2010, and 35,103.7 hectares by 2025. This increase represents a net gain of 22,936.15 hectares. Such growth shows significant expansion of agricultural land or degradation of vegetated areas, due to intensified cultivation, grazing, or exposure of land from declining vegetation cover.

Built-up areas’ result increases from a relatively modest extent of 10,188.9 hectares in 1990, to 18,367.9 hectares in 2000, 34,628.0 hectares in 2010, and surged to 69,589.3 hectares by 2024. The net increase of 59,400.42 hectares shows rapid urbanization, associated with population growth, infrastructure development, and settlement expansion. This trend illustrates the increasing pressure on land resources as human activities intensify within the study areas. Forest and vegetation cover had a declining trajectory. In 1990, these areas covered a vast 117,163.9 hectares. However, the extent gradually decreased to 115,283.1 hectares in 2000 and 113,585.3 hectares in 2010, then dropped more rapidly to 79,718.7 hectares in 2025. This change represents a total net loss of 37,445.2 hectares. The steady decline points to continued deforestation, habitat conversion, and ecological degradation trends commonly associated with land clearing for agriculture, fuelwood extraction, and encroaching development. The net reduction of nearly 37,500 hectares indicates the adverse impact of anthropogenic activities such as deforestation, agricultural expansion, and urban sprawl.

Table 4. Land Use Land Cover Trends and Net Changes over Three Decades (1990-2025) in the Study Areas (Okwango and Anape Range)

LULC	Total coverage(hectare)				Total area per LULC	Net Change between 1990 & 2024 (ha)
	1990	2000	2010	2025		
Farm/bare land area	12,167.5	12,769.0	30,510.9	35,103.7	90,551.1	22,936.15
Built-up area	10,188.9	18,367.9	34,628.0	69,589.3	132,774.1	59,400.42
Forest/vegetation area	117,163.9	115,283.1	113,585.3	79,718.7	425,751.1	-37,445.2
Total	139,520.3	146,420.0	178,724.2	184,411.7	649,076.3	44,891.35

Source: Field Survey, (2025)

The result of land use/land cover (LULC) patterns in the Okwango and Anape Ranges showed significant changes between 1990 and 2025 (Figure 3). The percentage of farm and bare land areas gradually increased, rising from 8.7% in 1990 to 19.0% in 2025. This expansion indicates a growth in agricultural activities within the study area. The built-up area had rapid growth, rising from 7.3% in 1990 to 37.7% in 2025. This significant increase showed the pace of settlements' growth and development due to population growth in the study area. However, the forest and vegetation cover exhibited a consistent decline, decreasing from 84.0% in 1990 to 43.2% in 2025. This downward trend revealed the impact of human activities and the expansion of settlements, which affect the area covered by the natural environment and ecosystems in the study area. These shifts in LULC patterns show the complex dynamics between human development and environmental sustainability in the study area (Okwango and Anape Range).

Figure 3. Percentage LULC from 1990 to 2025 in Okwango and Anape Ranges
Source: Field Survey, (2025)

The land use and land cover (forest/vegetation, farm/bare land, and built-up areas) maps presented in Figures 4 to 7 presented a temporal visualization of landscape changes in the study area (Anape and Okwango Range) between 1990 and 2025. Figure 6 shows the LULC map of Anape and Okwango Ranges from 1990, the 1990 LULC map dominated by forest and vegetation cover. At this early stage, natural ecosystems occupy the highest land area, indicating limited human intervention. Built-up and farm/bare land areas are scarcely represented, indicating minimal settlement expansion and low levels of land clearing. The spatial continuity of the vegetated zones shows a relatively undisturbed ecological structure.

By 2000, changes in land use patterns emerges, there is a modest increase in both built-up areas and farm/bare lands (Figure 4), implying the onset of localized urbanization and agricultural expansion. Although forest and vegetation cover remain the dominant class, early signs of fragmentation appear. This shows a gradual but steady transition from natural to human-modified landscapes, possibly driven by demographic growth and increased demand for land resources. The 2010 map (Figure 5) shows a more pronounced phase of land cover alteration. Built-up areas expand, occupying larger swathes of land that were previously under forest cover. Farm and bare lands also extend significantly, indicating intensified agricultural activities or further land degradation. The spatial pattern reveals increasing fragmentation of vegetated areas, reflecting the growing footprint of human settlements and associated infrastructure. This period signifies a transition into more accelerated landscape modification.

The 2025 LULC map (Figure 6) shows the current representation of land cover patterns of the study area. Based on the result, built-up areas are extensively distributed across the landscape, while farm and bare lands continue to increase. In contrast, forest and vegetation areas appear markedly reduced and highly fragmented, often confined to small and isolated patches. The extensive conversion of natural land into urban and agricultural uses reflects intensive anthropogenic pressure, with significant implications for ecosystem stability, biodiversity conservation, and environmental sustainability.

Figure 4. Land Use/Land Cover Map of the study areas 1990
Source: Field Survey, (2025)

Figure 5: Land Use/Land Cover Map of the study areas, 2000
Source: Field Survey, (2025)

Figure 6. Land Use/Land Cover Map of the study areas 2010
Source: Field Survey, (2025)

Figure 7. Land Use/Land Cover Map of the study areas 2025
Source: Field Survey, (2025)

Table 5 explained land use/land cover (LULC) transition matrices for three distinct periods: 1990–2000, 2000–2010, and 2010–2025, in the study area. The transition matrix between 1990 and 2000 indicates relatively minimal land cover transformation. Farm/bare land and built-up areas remained largely stable, with no recorded conversion from these classes into others during this decade. Forest and vegetation areas, however, had a low rate of change. A total of 8,179 hectares of forest were converted into built-up land, while 601.5 hectares were transformed into farm or bare land. Despite these changes, the forest area approximately 108,383.4 hectares remained intact. These findings show that, during this early phase, land conversion was relatively modest and primarily driven by localized urban development and agricultural encroachment into forested zones. Between 2000 and 2010, the study area had a high shift in land cover dynamics. Farm/bare land and built-up areas were stable, with no indication of conversion.

However, the forest and vegetation had increased fragmentation. Approximately 17,741.9 hectares of forest were converted to farm/bare land, while 16,260.1 hectares were lost to built-up areas. Only 79,583.3 hectares of forest remained unchanged by the end of this period. These figures show intensified land pressure and indicate the expansion of agriculture and settlements into previously forested landscapes. The forest-to-farm and forest-to-built-up transitions indicate a significant acceleration in land use change.

The period between 2010 to 2025 showed that Farm/bare land and built-up areas had no loss to other classes, indicating their permanence once conversion has occurred. However, forest and vegetation cover continue to be the primary source of land for expansion. During this period, approximately 4,592.8 hectares of forest were converted to farm or bare land, while 34,961.3 hectares were lost to built-up areas. Only 40,164.6 hectares of forest remained unaltered. This pattern reflects a high rate of urban expansion, far surpassing earlier decades, and signifies a critical turning point in the degradation of natural vegetation cover.

Table 5. Transition Matrix of LULC Changes (1990-2025) in the Study Areas

From \ To	Farm/Bare Land	Built-up Area	Forest/Vegetation	Total From
Transition Matrix of LULC Changes 1990-2000				
Farm/Bare Land	12,167.5	0	0	12,167.5
Built-up Area	0	10,188.9	0	10,188.9
Forest/Vegetation	601.5	8,179	108,383.4	117,163.9
Total	12,769	18,367.9	115,283.1	146,420
Transition Matrix of LULC Changes 2000-2010				
Farm/Bare Land	12,769	0	0	12,769
Built-up Area	0	18367.9	0	18367.9
Forest/Vegetation	17,741.9	16,260.1	79,583.3	113,585.3
Total	30,510.9	34,628	113,585.3	178,724.2
Transition Matrix of LULC Changes 2010-2025				
Farm/Bare Land	30,510.9	0	0	30,510.9
Built-up Area	0	34,628	0	34,628
Forest/Vegetation	4,592.8	3,4961.3	40,164.6	79,718.7
Total	35,103.7	69,589.3	79,718.7	184,411.7

Source: Field Survey, (2025)

Discussion

Understanding the effects of habitat loss on the distribution and abundance of species remains a leading question in ecology. For many years, explanations adopted either an ecological or an evolutionary standpoint, that is, whether species distribution and abundance was subject to particular environmental

determinants as inferred from correlative models or to differences in diversification timing and rates, respectively (Maurice, Fuashi, & Zeh, 2019).

The comparative findings on tree species diversity, distribution, abundance, and important value index in the study areas shows significant differences in various ecological metrics between the two ranges (Okwango and Anape). The Okwango range had 1,078 individual trees, marginally more than the Anape range, which had 1,065 individuals in its sample. The Okwango Range exhibits higher plants species richness and diversity than the Anape range, as indicated by different indices (Taxa_S, Shannon_H, Brillouin, Menhinick, Margalef, Fisher_alpha, and Chao-1).

However, Anape Range demonstrates greater evenness in species distribution, as reflected by the Evenness_e^H/S index. These findings highlight distinct ecological characteristics between the two ranges, with Okwango Range supporting a more diverse array of tree species, however, the Anape Range maintains a more balanced distribution of individuals among its species. The patterns observed in species distribution and important value index between the two Ranges indicate meaningful ecological differences. These disparities may be attributed to variations in soil quality, microclimate, previous disturbances, and human activities.

The use of Landsat imagery facilitated a more precise measurement of the amount of forest cover and how that forest is distributed than it was using previously available data. The visual trend of land use and land cover dynamics from 1990 to 2025 in the study areas portrayed significant anthropogenic pressure and rapid landscape transformation, particularly associated with settlements expansion and agricultural encroachment. Farm and bare land occupied a relatively modest area of approximately 12,167.5 hectares. Over time, this category increases, reaching 35,103.7 hectares. This growth indicates either the expansion of agricultural activity or the exposure of land due to vegetation clearance, possibly linked to deforestation or degradation processes.

The diameter distribution of tree stands is an essential aspect of forest structure analysis, which shows the trend, stand composition, regeneration status, and the developmental stage of the forest ecosystem. The diameter distribution pattern observed in the study areas (Okwango and Anape Range) implies a typical uneven-aged forest structure with healthy regeneration which have a limited presence of large-sized trees. The dominance of a few species in Anape Range implies a regenerating or structurally uniform forest, whereas Okwango's mixture of rare species and large trees diameter implies a more mature or selectively disturbed ecosystem.

The high frequency of small-diameter trees in Okwango Range indicates a forest in a dynamic state of regeneration. The lower frequency of large-diameter trees indicates past disturbances, natural mortality, or human exploitation (e.g., logging of large commercial trees). The presence of fewer large trees greater than nine hundred and ten centimetre in both ranges, is ecologically significant, as these trees contribute to canopy structure, biodiversity, and habitat stability.

The report on the population density indicates differences between the two ranges. The Cross River Gorilla exhibit a lower population densities (2.0 individual per km²) in Anape Range, and 0.0 individual per km² in Okwango Range. This variation in density revealed the spatial and ecological differences between the two Ranges and emphasize the importance of habitat availability and resource distribution in shaping the Gorilas population dynamics in the study area.

The higher decline rate shows the effects of agricultural encroachment, logging (as evidenced by high proportions of cut stems and chainsaw activity, and reduced habitat quality or connectivity). Therefore, the populations' status of Gorrila in the study areas is in decline, with a more severe situation evident in the Okwango Range. This widespread decrease call for an urgent need for enhanced protection measures, targeted anti-poaching efforts, and habitat restoration initiatives.

Conclusion

Forest and vegetation cover showed a steady decline throughout the period. The net reduction of nearly 37,500 hectares indicates the adverse impact of anthropogenic activities such as deforestation, agricultural expansion, and urban sprawl. The gorillas in this areas were more active or visible during the morning, possibly due to shifts in behaviour, such as foraging patterns or favourable environmental conditions such as low temperature indicating a significant contrast in the temporal activity patterns between the two ranges. The differences in the frequency of Cross River Gorilla encountered between the two ranges, implies that the species dynamics and distribution differs between the two Ranges, possibly influenced by factors such as food availability, social structures, and habitat preferences. These patterns in temporal and seasonal variation show the adaptive strategies of Gorilla species in response to environmental factors, with potential influences from food availability, temperature, and social behaviour influencing the Cross River Gorilla activity across different times and seasons.

Lack of fruits and Rainfall could be the possible reason why only one individual of Cross River Gorilla species was sighted during the rainy season while as high temperature could be the reason why only one individual was sighted in the dry season. While as the reason for the dropped in population in dry season could also be as a result of open vegetation in dry season or insufficient food materials such as fruits and lack of water.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made:

1. Land surveys should be carried out to determine the rate of encroachment into the Park by loggers and farmers.
2. Efforts should be made to adequately protect the study area, since it is one of the few location in the country where some valuable tropical and indigenous trees species can be found.

References

- Abondano, L. A., & Link, A. (2012). The social behaviour of brown spider monkeys (*Ateles hybridus*) in a fragmented forest in Colombia. *International Journal of Primatology*, 33(4), 769–783. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10764-012-9624-6>
- Arroyo-Rodríguez, V., Cuesta-del Moral, E., Mandujano, S., Chapman, C. A., Reyna-Hurtado, R., & Fahrig, L. (2013). Assessing habitat fragmentation effects on primates: The importance of evaluating questions at the correct scale. In L. K. Marsh & C. A. Chapman (Eds.), *Primates in fragments: Complexity and resilience* (pp. 13–28). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-8839-2_2
- Arroyo-Rodríguez, V., González-Perez, I. M., Garmendia, A., Solà, M., & Estrada, A. (2013). The relative impact of forest patch and landscape attributes on black howler populations in the fragmented Lacandona rainforest, Mexico. *Landscape Ecology*, 28(10), 1717–1727. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-013-9929-2>
- Benchimol, M., & Peres, C. A. (2013). Anthropogenic modulators of species–area relationships in Neotropical primates: A continental-scale analysis of fragmented forest landscapes. *Diversity and Distributions*, 19(11), 1339–1352. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12111>
- Boyle, S. A., & Smith, A. T. (2010). Can landscape and species characteristics predict primate presence in forest fragments in the Brazilian Amazon? *Biological Conservation*, 143(5), 1134–1143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2010.02.015>

- Campbell-Smith, G., Sembiring, R., & Linkie, M. (2012). Evaluating the effectiveness of human–orangutan conflict mitigation strategies in Sumatra. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 49(2), 367–375. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2012.02122.x>
- Carlsen, F., Leus, K., Traylor-Holzer, K., & McKenna, A. (2012). *Western chimpanzee population and habitat viability assessment for Sierra Leone: Final report*. IUCN/SSC Conservation Breeding Specialist Group – Europe (CBSG Europe).
- Carretero-Pinzón, X. (2016). *Conservation planning for primate communities in rapidly transforming landscapes* (Doctoral dissertation, The University of Queensland, School of Geography, Planning and Environmental Management). The University of Queensland eSpace. <https://espace.library.uq.edu.au/view/UQ:398697>
- Carretero-Pinzón, X., Defler, T. R., McAlpine, C. A., & Rhodes, J. R. (2016). What do we know about the effect of patch size on primate species across life history traits? *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 25(1), 37–66. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-015-1028-z>
- Chapman, C. A., Bonnell, T. R., Gogarten, J. F., Lambert, J. E., Omeja, P. A., Twinomugisha, D., Wasserman, M. D., & Rothman, J. M. (2013). Are primates ecosystem engineers? *International Journal of Primatology*, 34(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10764-012-9645-9>
- Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). (2010). *Global biodiversity outlook 3* (pp. 1–93). Montreal: Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity.
- Cronin, D. T., Riaco, C., & Hearn, G. W. (2013). Survey of threatened monkeys in the Iladyi River Valley region, southeastern Bioko Island, Equatorial Guinea. *African Primates*, 8(1), 1–8.
- Daily, G. C., Ceballos, G., Pacheco, J., Suzan, G., & Sánchez-Azofeifa, A. (2003). Countryside biogeography of Neotropical mammals: Conservation opportunities in agricultural landscapes of Costa Rica. *Conservation Biology*, 17(6), 1815–1826. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2003.00298.x>
- Defler, T. R. (2010). *Historia natural de los primates colombianos*. Bogotá: Universidad Nacional de Colombia.
- Donald, P. F. (2004). Biodiversity impacts of some agricultural commodity production systems. *Conservation Biology*, 18(1), 17–37. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2004.01803.x>
- Dunn, A., Bergl, R., Byler, D., Eben, E. S., Etiendem, D. N., Fotso, R., Ikfuingei, R., Imong, I., Jameson, C., Macfie, L., Morgan, B., Nchanji, A., Nicholas, L., Omeni, F., Oates, J., Pokempner, A., Sawyer, S., & Williamson, E. A. (2014). *Revised regional action plan for the conservation of the Cross River gorilla (Gorilla gorilla diehli)*. Primate Specialist Group & Wildlife Conservation Society.
- Estrada, A. (2009). Primate conservation in South America: The human and ecological dimensions of the problem. In P. A. Garber, A. Estrada, C. A. Bicca-Marques, E. W. Heymann, & K. B. Strier (Eds.), *South American primates: Comparative perspectives in the study of behavior, ecology, and conservation* (pp. 463–480). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-78705-3_18
- Fahrig, L., Baudry, J., Brotons, L., Burel, F. G., Crist, T. O., Fuller, R. J., Sirami, C., Siriwardena, G. M., & Martin, J. L. (2011). Functional landscape heterogeneity and animal biodiversity in agricultural landscapes. *Ecology Letters*, 14(2), 101–112. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2010.01574.x>
- Fitz, J., Adenle, A. A., & Speranza, C. I. (2022). Increasing signs of forest fragmentation in the Cross River National Park in Nigeria: Underlying drivers and need for sustainable responses. *Ecological Indicators*, 139, 108943. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2022.108943>
- Fox, J., Truong, D. M., Rambo, A. T., Tuyen, N. P., Cuc, L. T., & Leisz, S. J. (2000). Shifting cultivation: A new old paradigm for managing tropical forests. *BioScience*, 50(6), 521–528. [https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568\(2000\)050](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2000)050)

- Guisan, A., Tingley, R., Baumgartner, J. B., Naujokaitis-Lewis, I., Sutcliffe, P. R., Tulloch, A. I. T., Regan, T. J., Brotons, L., McDonald-Madden, E., Mantyka-Pringle, C., Martin, T. G., Rhodes, J. R., Maggini, R., Setterfield, S. A., Elith, J., Schwartz, M. W., Wintle, B. A., Broennimann, O., Austin, M., Ferrier, S., Kearney, M. R., Possingham, H. P., & Buckley, Y. M. (2013). Predicting species distributions for conservation decisions. *Ecology Letters*, *16*(11), 1424–1435. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12189>
- Haddad, N. M., Brudvig, L. A., Clobert, J., Davies, K. F., Gonzalez, A., Holt, R. D., Lovejoy, T. E., Sexton, J. O., Austin, M. P., Collins, C. D., Cook, W. M., Damschen, E. I., Ewers, R. M., Foster, B. L., Jenkins, C. N., King, A. J., Laurance, W. F., Levey, D. J., Margules, C. R., Melbourne, B. A., Nicholls, A. O., Orrock, J. L., Song, D., & Townshend, J. R. (2015). Habitat fragmentation and its lasting impact on Earth's ecosystems. *Science Advances*, *1*(2), e1500052. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1500052>
- Hansen, M. C., Potapov, P. V., Moore, R., Hancher, M., Turubanova, S. A., Tyukavina, A., Thau, D., Stehman, S. V., Goetz, S. J., Loveland, T. R., Kommareddy, A., Egorov, A., Chini, L., Justice, C. O., & Townshend, J. R. G. (2013). High-resolution global maps of 21st-century forest cover change. *Science*, *342*(6160), 850–853. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1244693>
- Heller, K., Baur, B., Lindenmayer, D., Margules, C., Saunders, D. A., & Wissel, C. (2004). Species survival in fragmented landscapes: Where are we now? *Biological Conservation*, *13*(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:BIOC.0000018450.89941.0e>
- Jones, J. P. G., Andriamarivololona, M. M., & Hockley, N. (2008). The importance of taboos and social norms to conservation in Madagascar. *Conservation Biology*, *22*(4), 976–986. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.2008.00970.x>
- Kelhoukhrienuo Metha, K., Mechülho, K., Tsüküri, L., Rüpree, M., Shijoh, M., Solo, N., Theünuo, R., Metha, R., & Metha, T. (2023, April 1). *Report writing on Environmental Studies (EVS) field trip: Habitat loss (Group 3)* (Unpublished field trip report). B.A. 6th Semester, Kohima College, Department of Environmental Studies.
- Kellerman, N. (Author-Compiler). (n.d.). *The way it is...: Hard facts and despicable truths – The drivers behind veganism* (A vegan reference book). [Self-published].
- Laurance, W. F. (2010). Habitat destruction: Death by a thousand cuts. In N. S. Sodhi & P. R. Ehrlich (Eds.), *Conservation biology for all* (pp. 73–87). Oxford University Press.
- Laurance, W. F., Nascimento, H. E. M., Laurance, S. G., Andrade, A., Ewers, R. M., Harms, K. E., Luizão, R. C. C., & Ribeiro, J. E. (2007). Habitat fragmentation, variable edge effects, and the landscape-divergence hypothesis. *PLoS ONE*, *2*(10), e1017. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0001017>
- Marsh, L. K., Chapman, C. A., Arroyo-Rodríguez, V., Cobden, A. K., Dunn, J. C., Gabriel, D., Ghai, R., Nijman, V., Reyna-Hurtado, R., Serio-Silva, J. C., & Wasserman, M. D. (2013). Primates in fragments 10 years later: Once and future goals. In L. K. Marsh & C. A. Chapman (Eds.), *Primates in fragments: Complexity and resilience* (pp. 503–523). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-8839-2_27
- Martin, A. E., & Fahrig, L. (2012). Measuring and selecting scales of effect for landscape predictors in species–habitat models. *Ecological Applications*, *22*(8), 2277–2292. <https://doi.org/10.1890/11-2241.1>
- Maurice, M. E., Fuashi, N. A., & Zeh, A. F. (2019). The effects of habitat fragmentation on the distribution of primates in the Kimbi-Fungom National Park, North West Region, Cameroon. *MOJ Ecology & Environmental Sciences*, *4*(2), 60–68. <https://doi.org/10.15406/mojes.2019.04.00135>
- Menz, M. H. M., Dixon, K. W., & Hobbs, R. J. (2013). Hurdles and opportunities for landscape-scale restoration. *Science*, *339*(6119), 526–527. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1228334>
- Mittermeier, R. A., Rylands, A. B., & Wilson, D. E. (2013). *Handbook of the mammals of the world*. Lynx Edicions.

- Morante-Filho, J. C., Faria, D., Mariano-Neto, E., & Rhodes, J. (2015). Birds in anthropogenic landscapes: The responses of ecological groups to forest loss in the Brazilian Atlantic Forest. *PLoS ONE*, *10*(6), e0128923. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0128923>
- National Wildlife Federation. (n.d.). *Habitat loss*. In *Wildlife guide: Threats to wildlife*. National Wildlife Federation. Retrieved November 27, 2025, from <https://www.nwf.org/Educational-Resources/Wildlife-Guide/Threats-to-Wildlife/Habitat-Loss>
- Nneji, L. M., Adeola, A. C., Adedeji, B. E., Oladipo, O. G., Okeyoyin, A. O., & Awodiran, M. O. (2021). Species richness, distribution pattern, and conservation status of amphibians in Cross River National Park, south-eastern Nigeria. *Biologia*, *76*(11), 2573–2588. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11756-021-00751-8>
- Olory, C. S. (2018). Contributions of Cross River National Park to national development: Prospects and challenges. In *Proceedings of the 6th NSCB Biodiversity Conference* (pp. 309–315). University of Uyo.
- Oskarsson, S. (2014). *Community engagement in wildlife conservation* (Master's thesis, Halmstad University, Master's Programme in Applied Environmental Science). Halmstad University.
- Pardini, R., Bueno, A. A., Gardner, T. A., Prado, P. I., & Metzger, J. P. (2010). Beyond the fragmentation threshold hypothesis: Regime shifts in biodiversity across fragmented landscapes. *PLoS ONE*, *5*(10), e13666. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0013666>
- Peek, P. M., & Yankah, K. (2004). *African folklore: An encyclopedia* (pp. 130–136). Routledge.
- Poulin, J. P., & Villard, M. A. (2011). Edge effect and matrix influence on the nest survival of an old forest specialist, the brown creeper (*Certhia americana*). *Landscape Ecology*, *26*(7), 911–922. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-011-9616-y>
- Pyritz, L. W., Büntgen, A. B. S., Herzog, S. K., & Kessler, M. (2010). Effects of habitat structure and fragmentation on diversity and abundance of primates in tropical deciduous forests in Bolivia. *International Journal of Primatology*, *31*(5), 796–812. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10764-010-9436-0>
- Rylands, A. B., Williamson, E. A., Hoffmann, M., & Mittermeier, R. A. (2008). Primate surveys and conservation assessments. *Oryx*, *42*(3), 313–314. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0030605308000567>
- Schipper, J., Chanson, J. S., Chiozza, F., Cox, N. A., Hoffmann, M., Katariya, V., Lamoreux, J., Rodrigues, A. S. L., Stuart, S. N., Temple, H. J., Baillie, J., Boitani, L., Lacher, T. E., Jr., Mittermeier, R. A., et al. (2008). The status of the world's land and marine mammals: Diversity, threat, and knowledge. *Science*, *322*(5899), 225–230. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1165115>
- Schwitzer, C., Mittermeier, R. A., Rylands, A. B., Chiozza, F., Williamson, E. A., Wallis, J., & Cotton, A. (Eds.). (2015). *Primates in peril: The world's 25 most endangered primates 2014–2016*. IUCN SSC Primate Specialist Group, International Primatological Society, Conservation International, & Bristol Zoological Society.
- Thornton, D. H., Branch, L. C., & Sunquist, M. E. (2011). The relative influence of habitat loss and fragmentation: Do tropical mammals meet the temperate paradigm? *Ecological Applications*, *21*(6), 2324–2333. <https://doi.org/10.1890/10-2206.1>
- Turner, M. G., Gardner, R. H., & O'Neill, R. V. (2001). *Landscape ecology in theory and practice: Pattern and process*. Springer.
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2009). *Human development report: Overcoming barriers – Human mobility and development*. United Nations Development Programme. <http://hdr.undp.org/en/media/HDR>

Villard, M. A., & Metzger, J. P. (2014). Beyond the fragmentation debate: A conceptual model to predict when habitat configuration really matters. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 51(2), 309–318. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12190>

Wikipedia contributors. (n.d.). *Cross River gorilla*. In *Wikipedia*. Retrieved November 27, 2025, from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki?curid=28024638>

Wildlife Conservation Society Nigeria. (n.d.). *Cross River National Park (Okwangwo Division)*. Wildlife Conservation Society. Retrieved November 27, 2025, from <https://nigeria.wcs.org/Wild-Places/Cross-River-NP-Okwangwo.aspx>

Wu, J., & Li, H. (2006). Concepts of scale and scaling. In J. Wu, K. B. Jones, H. Li, & O. L. Loucks (Eds.), *Scaling and uncertainty analysis in ecology: Methods and applications* (pp. 3–15). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-4663-4_1

Yager, G. O., Alarape, A. A., Onaji, O. J., & Acha, S. (2022). Impact of anthropogenic activities on vegetation cover and mammalian herbivores in Afi Mountain Wildlife Sanctuary, Cross River State, Nigeria. *World News of Natural Sciences*, 41, 51–73. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7079020>

Appendix

Table 2. Tree Species Distribution and Importance Values Index in the Study Area

Scientific names	Family Names	Anape range					Okwango range				
		Freq.	BA	RD	Rdo	IVI	Freq.	BA	RD	Rdo	IVI
<i>Alafia barteri</i>	Apocynaceae	-	-	-	-	-	18	0.67	1.67	0.61	1.14
<i>Albizia zygia</i>	Fabaceae	-	-	-	-	-	8	0.82	0.74	0.73	0.74
<i>Allablackia floribunda</i>	Fabaceae	-	-	-	-	-	98	1.24	9.09	1.11	5.10
<i>Amphimas pterocarpoides</i>	Fabaceae	-	-	-	-	-	18	0.70	1.67	0.63	1.15
<i>Ancistrophyllum secundiflorum</i>	Phyllanthaceae	-	-	-	-	-	7	0.45	0.65	0.41	0.53
<i>Andira inermis</i>	Fabaceae	-	-	-	-	-	12	0.38	1.11	0.34	0.73
<i>Anogeisus leiocarpa</i>	Combretaceae	7	0.81	0.66	0.56	0.61	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Antiaris toxicaria</i>	Moraceae	55	6.54	5.16	4.54	4.85	2	0.58	0.19	0.53	0.36
<i>Antrocaryon micraster</i>	Anacardiaceae	2	12.68	0.19	8.80	4.50	2	0.51	0.19	0.46	0.32
<i>Bambax boeaopozense</i>	Malvaceae	-	-	-	-	-	1	19.64	0.09	17.70	8.90
<i>Baphia nitida</i>	Fabaceae	51	3.72	4.79	2.58	3.69	80	0.45	7.42	0.40	3.91
<i>Baphia pubescens</i>	Fabaceae	-	-	-	-	-	4	0.47	0.37	0.42	0.40
<i>Barteria nigrimana</i>	Passifloraceae	-	-	-	-	-	7	0.22	0.65	0.20	0.42
<i>Bombax buonopozense</i>	Malvaceae	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.87	0.09	0.78	0.44
<i>Brachystegia eurycoma</i>	Fabaceae	40	3.52	3.76	2.44	3.10	2	0.41	0.19	0.37	0.28
<i>Brenania brieyi</i>	Rubiaceae	7	2.49	0.66	1.73	1.19	23	0.79	2.13	0.71	1.42
<i>Canarium schweinfurthii</i>	Burseraceae	-	-	-	-	-	20	0.60	1.86	0.54	1.20
<i>Canthium subcordatum</i>	Rubiaceae	12	6.19	1.13	4.29	2.71	31	0.77	2.88	0.69	1.78
<i>Carapa procera</i>	Meliaceae	-	-	-	-	-	5	0.30	0.46	0.27	0.37
<i>Christiana Africana</i>	Malvaceae	110	3.48	10.33	2.41	6.37	20	0.68	1.86	0.61	1.23

<i>Chrysophyllum albidum</i>	Sapotaceae	-	-	-	-	-	2	0.24	0.19	0.22	0.20
<i>Cola acuminata</i>	Malvaceae	-	-	-	-	-	17	0.44	1.58	0.39	0.98
<i>Cola altissima</i>	Malvaceae	-	-	-	-	-	4	0.22	0.37	0.20	0.28
<i>Cola caricifolia</i>	Malvaceae	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.04	0.09	0.04	0.06
<i>Cola gigantean</i>	Malvaceae	-	-	-	-	-	7	1.30	0.65	1.17	0.91
<i>Cola lepidota</i>	Malvaceae	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.67	0.09	0.60	0.35
<i>Cola millenii</i>	Malvaceae	19	1.47	1.78	1.02	1.40	1	0.94	0.09	0.85	0.47
<i>Cordia Africana</i>	Boraginaceae	10	0.95	0.94	0.66	0.80	4	0.59	0.37	0.53	0.45
<i>Coryanthe pachyceras</i>	Rubiaceae	-	-	-	-	-	3	0.26	0.28	0.23	0.26
<i>Coula edulis</i>	Olacaceae	-	-	-	-	-	19	0.78	1.76	0.70	1.23
<i>Cylicodicus gabunensis</i>	Olacaceae	-	-	-	-	-	65	2.64	6.03	2.38	4.20
<i>Dalbergia latifolia</i>	Fabaceae	29	0.62	2.72	0.43	1.58	30	0.62	2.78	0.55	1.67
<i>Dillenia indica</i>	Dilleniaceae	-	-	-	-	-	3	0.25	0.28	0.22	0.25
<i>Distemonanthus benthamianus</i>	Fabaceae	17	1.57	1.60	1.09	1.34	21	4.09	1.95	3.69	2.82
<i>Entandophragma angolense</i>	Meliaceae	35	7.20	3.29	5.00	4.14	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Entandrophragma utile</i>	Meliaceae	-	-	-	-	-	15	0.36	1.39	0.32	0.86
<i>Erythrophleum guaveolens</i>	Fabaceae	-	-	-	-	-	2	1.53	0.19	1.38	0.78
<i>Gossweilerodendron balsamiferum</i>	Fabaceae	3	5.97	0.28	4.14	2.21	24	1.26	2.23	1.14	1.68
<i>Guarea thompsonii</i>	Meliaceae	-	-	-	-	-	4	0.36	0.37	0.32	0.35
<i>Hannoa undulata</i>	Simaroubaceae	22	0.98	2.07	0.68	1.37	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Harungana madagascarensis</i>	Hypericaceae	62	5.06	5.82	3.51	4.67	18	0.42	1.67	0.38	1.03
<i>Heinsia crinata</i>	Rubiaceae	-	-	-	-	-	20	0.36	1.86	0.33	1.09
<i>Holarrhena floribunda</i>	Apocynaceae	2	0.76	0.19	0.53	0.36	2	0.10	0.19	0.09	0.14
<i>Iringia gabonensis</i>	Irvingiaceae	41	2.70	3.85	1.87	2.86	89	0.60	8.26	0.54	4.40
<i>Khaya grandifoliola</i>	Meliaceae	25	1.63	2.35	1.13	1.74	5	1.08	0.46	0.97	0.72
<i>Lophira alata</i>	Ochnaceae	1	0.64	0.09	0.45	0.27	10	2.67	0.93	2.41	1.67

<i>Lovoa trichilioides</i>	Meliaceae	38	7.72	3.57	5.35	4.46		40	0.90	3.71	0.81	2.26
<i>Maesobotrya barteri</i>	Phyllanthaceae	-	-	-	-	-		9	0.65	0.83	0.58	0.71
<i>Malacantha alnifolia</i>	Rubiaceae	-	-	-	-	-		1	0.79	0.09	0.71	0.40
<i>Manniophyton fulvum</i>	Euphorbiaceae	90	4.96	8.45	3.44	5.95		1	0.63	0.09	0.57	0.33
<i>Mansonia altissima</i>	Malvaceae	8	0.59	0.75	0.41	0.58		26	0.34	2.41	0.30	1.36
<i>Marianthus erubescens</i>	Pittosporaceae	1	4.31	0.09	2.99	1.54		4	0.45	0.37	0.40	0.39
<i>Milicia excels</i>	Moraceae	19	2.11	1.78	1.47	1.63		1	0.62	0.09	0.55	0.32
<i>Musanga cercropiodes</i>	Cecropiaceae	-	-	-	-	-		3	1.37	0.28	1.24	0.76
<i>Ochna serrulata</i>	Ochnaceae	59	6.43	5.54	4.46	5.00		4	1.17	0.37	1.05	0.71
<i>Ochroma lagopus</i>	Malvaceae	26	1.08	2.44	0.75	1.59		2	0.90	0.19	0.81	0.50
<i>Omphalocarpum elatum</i>	Sapotaceae	-	-	-	-	-		1	25.71	0.09	23.16	11.63
<i>Oxyanthus speciosus</i>	Rubiaceae	-	-	-	-	-		5	1.62	0.46	1.46	0.96
<i>Pauridiantha paucinerwis</i>	Rubiaceae	-	-	-	-	-		8	0.31	0.74	0.28	0.51
<i>Pentaclethra macrophylla</i>	Fabaceae	30	3.46	2.82	2.40	2.61		12	1.44	1.11	1.30	1.21
<i>Peterodendron ovatum</i>	Achariaceae	-	-	-	-	-		4	0.40	0.37	0.36	0.37
<i>Picralima nitida</i>	Apocynaceae	70	4.49	6.57	3.12	4.85		1	0.64	0.09	0.58	0.34
<i>Piptadeniastrum africanum</i>	Fabaceae	28	9.77	2.63	6.78	4.71		2	0.09	0.19	0.08	0.13
<i>Pterocarpus erinaceus</i>	Fabaceae	-	-	-	-	-		4	1.88	0.37	1.70	1.03
<i>Pterocarpus santalinoides</i>	Fabaceae	-	-	-	-	-		42	0.70	3.90	0.63	2.26
<i>Pterocarpus soyauxii</i>	Fabaceae	17	2.32	1.60	1.61	1.60		-	-	-	-	-
<i>Pterodendron erinaceus</i>	Fabaceae	-	-	-	-	-		10	6.85	0.93	6.18	3.55
<i>Pycnanthus angolense</i>	Myristicaceae	3	1.82	0.28	1.26	0.77		39	2.40	3.62	2.16	2.89
<i>Rauwolfia vomitoria</i>	Apocynaceae	63	5.05	5.92	3.50	4.71		1	0.36	0.09	0.32	0.21
<i>Rothmania hispida</i>	Rubiaceae	-	-	-	-	-		11	0.39	1.02	0.35	0.69
<i>Rothmannia capensis</i>	Rubiaceae	-	-	-	-	-		1	0.26	0.09	0.23	0.16
<i>Spathodea campanulata</i>	Bignoniaceae	-	-	-	-	-		9	0.99	0.83	0.89	0.86

<i>Sterculia oblonga</i>	Malvaceae	-	-	-	-	-	32	0.52	2.97	0.47	1.72
<i>Strombosia grandifolia</i>	Olacaceae	-	-	-	-	-	16	1.27	1.48	1.14	1.31
<i>Symphonia globulifera</i>	Clusiaceae	-	-	-	-	-	7	0.61	0.65	0.55	0.60
<i>Tabanaemontana pachysiphon</i>	Apocynaceae	30	3.66	2.82	2.54	2.68	11	0.66	1.02	0.59	0.81
<i>Terminalia superba</i>	Combretaceae	17	10.29	1.60	7.14	4.37	7	1.06	0.65	0.96	0.80
<i>Triclepisium madagascariensis</i>	Poaceae	-	-	-	-	-	18	1.15	1.67	1.04	1.35
<i>Triplochiton scleroxylon</i>	Malvaceae	-	-	-	-	-	2	0.44	0.19	0.40	0.29
<i>Upaca guineensis</i>	Phyllanthaceae	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.50	0.09	0.45	0.27
<i>Voacanga Africana</i>	Apocynaceae	16	7.05	1.50	4.90	3.20	11	0.29	1.02	0.26	0.64
<i>Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides</i>	Rutaceae	-	-	-	-	-	6	0.28	0.56	0.26	0.41

Note: Freq. is frequency of species, BA is basal area, RD is relative density, RDo is relative Dominance, IVI is important Value Index of species.

Source: Field Survey, (2025).

